

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF SOME TIPS AND STRATEGIES OF IELTS WRITING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890881>

Annotation. This study aims to improve students' speaking skills at the Department of English. Based on interviews carried out to get initial data on the students' speaking skills, it was shown that the students had problems in speaking due to inadequate knowledge of the language which in turn made the students felt unconfident to speak. The students were not familiar with various speaking activities facilitating them to speak. They read text to convey ideas and a lack of strategies when speaking. To help the students, task-based learning was adapted through action research in one-semester courses. Fifteen students in the third semester participated in this study. The data were taken from the results of the pre-test to post-test, interview, and observation. The findings reveal that the use of task-based learning helps the students improve their speaking skills of three indicators assessed: accuracy, vocabulary, and comprehension. The students manage to complete the tasks by conducting various activities through three phases of learning: the pre-task, task-cycle, and form focus. They succeed in improving their speaking skills and gaining their confidence. The students can evaluate their learning in pairs and group works.

Key words: Students' Speaking skills; Task-based learning; Speaking While it is a bit of exaggeration, students clearly feel that classroom-based speaking practice does not prepare them for the real world.

Why do students so often highlight listening and speaking as their biggest problems?

Partly because of the demands of listening and speaking and partly because of the way speaking is often taught. It usually consists of language practice activities (discussions, information-gap activities etc.) or is used to practice a specific grammar point. Neither teaches patterns of real interaction. So, what can we do in the classroom to prepare students for real interaction? What do students need? Practical suggestions What language should I teach?

How do I get students to use new language Further reading What do students need? Practice at using L1 (mother tongue) strategies, which they don't automatically transfer. An awareness of formal / informal language and practice at choosing appropriate language for different situations. The awareness that informal spoken language is less complex than written language. It uses shorter sentences, is less organized and uses more 'vague' or non-specific language. Exposure to a variety of spoken text types. The ability to cope with different listening situations. Many listening exercises involve students as 'overhearers' even though most communication is face-to-face. To be competent at both 'message-oriented' or transactional language and interactional language, language for maintaining social relationships. To be taught patterns of real interaction. To have intelligible pronunciation and be able to cope with streams of speech. Rehearsal time. By giving students guided preparation / rehearsal time they are more likely to use a wider range of language in a spoken task. Practical suggestions Transferring L1 strategies When preparing for a spoken task, make students aware of any relevant L1 strategies that might help them to perform the task successfully. For example, 'rephrasing' if someone does not understand what they mean. Formal / informal language Give students one or more short dialogues where one speaker is either too formal or informal. Students first identify the inappropriate language, then try to change it. Also show students how disorganized informal speech is. Vague language Using tape scripts of informal speech, focus on examples of vague language.

Draw up a list of spoken text types relevant to the level of your class. Teach the language appropriate for each text type. Interactive listening Develop interactive listening exercises. Face-to-face listening is the most common and the least practiced by course books. Any form of 'Live listening' (the teacher speaking to the students) is suitable. Transactional and interactional language Raise students' awareness by using a dialogue that contains both. It could be two friends chatting to each other (interactional) and ordering a meal (transactional). Real interaction patterns Teach real interaction patterns. Introduce the following basic interactional pattern: Initiate, Respond, Follow-up. This is a simplification of Amy Tsui's work. See Tsui (1994) The following interaction could be analyzed as follows: perform the task. Rather than just give students 10 minutes to prepare and rehearse the task, give students guided preparation time. A simple preparation guide for the task could be a few key questions like: How will you start the conversation? What topics are you going to talk about? How are you going to move from one topic to another? How are

you going to end the conversation? After the preparation stage, students give a 'live performance'. This can be in front of the class or group to group in a large class. This increases motivation and adds an element of real-life stress. Another way of encouraging students to use new language in a communication activity is to make a game out of it. Give students a situation and several key phrases to include. They get points for using the language. Similarly, when working on the language of discussion, you can produce a set of cards with the key phrases/exponents on. The cards are laid out in front of each group of 2/3/4 students. If a student uses the language on a particular card appropriately during the discussion, he/she keeps the card. The student with the most cards wins. If he/she uses the language inappropriately, then he / she can be challenged and has to leave the card on the table.

Students may have the below mentioned, expected barriers to express themselves in speaking situations. There might be other barriers also existing depending on the cultural background, social interaction, and institutional behavior and family setup. Listed here are the most common „speaking“ problems.

- a. Lack of Grammar Exposure
- b. Lack of vocabulary
- c. Lack of regular practice
- d. Hesitation or Shyness to start
- e. Fear of public speaking
- f. Mispronunciation
- g. Delay in thinking process
- h. Influence and comfort zone of mother tongue
- i. Delivery of the content

In summary. The purpose of any degree or academics is to obtain a job and to make ones livelihood better. When the speaking skill is acquired, it will enhance the confidence level to attend job interviews. The students who are going to be candidates for the upcoming days will have to get through different types of assessments and interviews. If it is an aptitude or reasoning questions they can understand the questions through the English language only. In the case of group discussion or personal interview, again they have to speak in English fluently and proficiently. If it is pre-placement or post-placement the speaking skill is mandatory. In the case of higher education or obtaining placement in the competitive job market speaking in English and the importance of language is undeniable. As a result, if a candidate can speak in English with a good presence

of mind, it will enable them to obtain their dream job. Even if the candidate is technically sound, to express his ideas, English speaking skill is the tool to communicate, however, the importance of speaking skills cannot be neglected. The teacher has to train the students consciously, keeping in mind to make her students acquire speaking skills and help them with all the possible or innovative activities to let them in a speaking driven classroom. She or he should make them understand the importance practically by quoting real-time examples and pieces of evidence. And students also should be responsible enough to follow the instructions closely and maintain an interactive and continuous practicing platform to be established. Thus, the paper identifies the barriers in English speaking in different situations and suggest possible and effective ways to hone and perfect their speaking skill as it is an inevitable tool for employability.

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